

GL MICAVE

D7.3 Report on the standardization landscape and applicable standards

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Executive summary

The Spanish Association for Standardization (UNE) is the Spanish Standardization Body member of CEN, CENELEC, ETSI, ISO, IEC and COPANT and is partner of GLOMICAVE to provide support regarding the standardization tasks included in the task 7.4 Standardization activities developed through two subtasks, 7.4.1 Analysis of the applicable standardization landscape and 7.4.2 Contribution to the ongoing and future standardization developments.

The main objective of the subtask 7.4.1 of GLOMICAVE project is provide useful information for the development of the project and its work packages, ensured compatibility and interoperability with what already exists in the market by identification the existing standards in the fields related with the GLOMICAVE needs. To fulfil this commitment, UNE has prepared the deliverable D7.3 "Report on standardization landscape and applicable standards" which provide useful information in the identifying the committees of standardization and the standards existing in the fields related with the GLOMICAVE. The availability of this information at the very early stage of the projects will allow using already existing material and the alignment with current and under development standardization works facilitating the compatibility of the outcomes with the current market practises.

The results of D7.3 are the starting point of D7.4 "Report on the contribution to standardization".

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List of abbreviations

AFNOR	Association Française de Normalisation
AG	Advisory Group
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMD	Amedment
API	Application Programming Interface
AWI	Amedment Work Item
BDA	Big Data Analytics
BSI	British Standard Institution
CAG	Chairman´s Advisory Group
CD	Committee Draft
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENENLEC(CLC)	European Committee for Standardization in the Electrical field
CLC	CENELEC
CWA	CEN or CENELEC Workshop Agreement
DAMD	Draft Amedment
DIN	Deutsches Institut fur Normung
DIS	Draft Internactional Standard
DTR	Draft Technical Report
DTS	Draft Technical Specification
EC	European Commission
EN	European Standard
ESO	European Standardization Organization
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FDIS	Final Draft Internactional Standard
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization; International Standard
IT	Information technology
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
IWA	International Workshop Agreement
JAG	Join Advisory Group
JTC	Join Technical Committee
SC	Subcommittee
SMB	Standardization Management Board
TC	Technical Committee
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
UNE	Spanish Association for Standardization
WD	Working Draft
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Introduction

The purpose of this report D7.3 is to provide information on standardization landscape, by identifying relevant standards to GLOMICAVE project; is also to provide an overview of standards development by the Standardization Committees.

It pretends to provide starting information for the Work Packages ensuring compatibility and interoperability with already existing solutions by identifying relevant standards and standard projects under development at International/European levels in the fields of Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, Genomics, Cybersecurity, Cloud, Food products and Environment.

1. CONCEPTS

1.1 Project presentation overview

GLOMICAVE project is funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2018 - 2020); the project runs for 42 months. It brings together 15 partners from 6 different European countries.

The main objective of GLOMICAVE is to develop a cloud-based genotype to phenotype platform – relying on Big Data Analytics (BDA) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques – and using large-scale publicly available and experimental omics datasets, enhanced with an automatic processing of scientific literature.

The main outcome will be a multi-omics data analysis open platform consisting of multiple tools to assist experts and non-experts in identifying and understanding new links between genotype and phenotype, which apply to different domains. The platform will tackle data integration, analysis, and exploitation, with special attention to data governance, security, management and monitoring.

GLOMICAVE integrative approach will be validated in 3 different industrial sectors (livestock, agrobiotechnology and environment) addressing specific challenges in 6 business cases (animal reproductive technology, meat quality, fruit growth and quality, plant growth, phosphorus removal/recovery and bioenergy production in the urban water cycle), which will pave the way for further uptake in other business areas.

1.2 Short introduction about standardization

Standards are voluntary technical documents that set out requirements for a specific item, material, component, system, or service, or describes in detail a particular method, procedure or best practice. Standards are developed and defined through a process of sharing knowledge and building consensus among technical experts nominated by interested parties and other stakeholders - including businesses, consumers and environmental groups, among others. These experts are organized in Technical Committees (TCs), which are subdivided in Subcommittees (SCs) or Working Groups (WGs). These TCs are included in the structure of the Standardization Organizations (National, European and International, with the respective mirror committees) and work following their internal regulations.

The standardization bodies operate at National (UNE, AFNOR, BSI, DIN, etc.), Regional (CEN, CENELEC, ETSI) or International (ISO, IEC, ITU) level. Sometimes there are different standardization bodies at the same level but covering different fields. This is the case of ISO (general), IEC (electrical) and ITU (telecommunications) at International level, or CEN, CENELEC and ETSI at European level in the same way.

There are also different kinds of standardization documents. The most widespread is the standard, which has a different code depending on the organization under it was developed, e.g. EN for European Standards, ISO for International standards. Other types of documents are Technical Specifications (TS), Technical Reports (TR) and Workshop Agreements (CWA). Further Amendments to the standards are identified by adding A1, A2, etc. at the end of the standard code.

The formal definition of a standard is a “document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body that provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context”. These include requirements and/or recommendations in relation to products, systems, processes, or services. European Standards (ENs) are documents that have been ratified by one of the three European Standardization Organizations (ESOs), CEN, CENELEC or ETSI; recognized as competent in the area of voluntary technical standardization as for the EU Regulation 1025/2012.

At European level, all the members of CEN shall adopt EN standards as national standards and **must** withdraw any existing national standard which could conflict with them. A summary of the characteristics of the different standardization documents can be found in table 1.

Table 1 – Characteristics of different standardization documents.

Type	International code	European code	National code	Main characteristics
Standard	ISO IEC	EN	UNE, NF, BS, DIN, etc. When adopting: UNE-EN, NF-EN, UNE-ISO, NF-ISO, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: 3 years • 2 steps of member approval • European: compulsory national adoption - Revision: every 5 years
Technical Specification (TS)	ISO/TS IEC/TS	CEN/TS CLC/TS	When adopting: UNE-CEN/TS, NF-CEN/TS, UNE-ISO/TS, NF-ISO/TS, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: 21 months • 1 step of member approval or internal approval in TC • European: optional national adoption - Revision: at 3 years (upgrading to EN or deletion)
Technical Report (TR)	ISO/TR IEC/TR	CEN/TR CLC/TR	When adopting: UNE-CEN/TR, NF-CEN/TR, UNE-ISO/TR, NF-ISO/TR, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: free timeframe • Internal approval in TC • European: optional national adoption - No revision required
Workshop Agreement	IWA	CWA	Variable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration: free timeframe (usually few months) • Internal approval in the Workshop • European: optional national adoption - Revision: at 3 years (upgrading to EN or deletion)

There is also an agreement established between European and International Organizations (e.g. CEN and ISO) in order to avoid duplication of efforts and promote global relevance of standards, which allows to adopt or develop in parallel each other's standards with the same content and code. National

standards could also be proposed as a base for new European or International standards. The following figure 1 shows the possible tracks of the standards.

Figure 1 – Possible tracks of standards adoption.

Therefore, the code of any standard is the combination of the above-mentioned issues and could be explained as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 – Example of identification of elements in the code of a standard.

2. METHODOLOGY

For the identification of standards and standards under development relevant for GLOMICAVE project the following methodology has been followed:

—A list of key concepts has been prepared to act as a starting point for the identification of standardization areas.

For the selection of the key concepts the aims and goals of the project and the levels in which the project should integrate were considered. The list of key concepts used for the search is shown in table 2.

Table 2 – List of key concepts acting as start point for the identification of standardization areas.

1. Biogas	3.1 Biogas
2. Algorithm	3.2 Information technology
3. API (Application Programming Interface)	3.2 Information technology
4. Artificial Intelligence	3.2 Information technology
5. Big Data	3.2 Information technology
6. Information Systems	3.2 Information technology
7. Data Governance	3.2 Information technology
8. Cloud	3.2 Information technology
9. Cybersecurity	3.2 Information technology
10. Genomics	3.2 Information technology
11. Environment	3.3 Environmental management
12. Biomarker	3.4 Food products
13. Food products	3.4 Food products
14. Sludge	3.5 Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment and disposal

- Standards and standards under development have been identified for each standardization area, together with the technical committee responsible for the respective standards.

The search covered the European standardization developed by the European Committee for Standardization (CEN), European Committee for Standardization in the Electrical field CENELEC (CLC) and International standardization developed by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and IEC. The databases and websites used for the search are referred in the chapter of references.

- As a result of the searching process a first draft has prepared by UNE: 47 pages including technical bodies, developed standards and standards under development. This draft has been sent to GLOMICAVE partners to identify if it is necessary to include new concepts, new committees or new standards and projects of standards and also the partners have to specified in what WP it would be used.

3. RELEVANT COMMITTEES, STANDARDS AND PROJECTS OF STANDARDS FOR GLOMICAVE

Based on the concepts identified in chapter 2, the relevant committees for these concepts have been sought and all the standards published by these committees have been reviewed as well as the standard projects under development to carry out this chapter.

3.1 Biogas

Technical Committee:

1. ISO/TC 255 Biogas

i. Scope:

Standardization in the field of biogas produced by anaerobic digestion, gasification from biomass and power to gas from biomass sources.

ii. Structure:

ISO/TC 255/WG 1	Terms, definitions and classification scheme for the production, conditioning and utilization of biogas
ISO/TC 255/WG 2	Flares for biogas plants
ISO/TC 255/WG 3	Domestic biogas installations (household and small farm scale)
ISO/TC 255/WG 4	Safety and environmental aspects
ISO/TC 255/WG 5	Biogas systems – Non-household
ISO/TC 255/WG 6	Biomass gasification

iii. Standards:

3 published ISO standards <https://www.iso.org/committee/617083/x/catalogue/p/1/u/0/w/0/d/0>, but we consider relevant for GLOMICAVE the following:

- ISO 20675:2018 Biogas — Biogas production, conditioning, upgrading and utilization — Terms, definitions and classification scheme

This document defines terms and describes classifications related to biogas production by anaerobic digestion, gasification from biomass and power to gas from biomass sources, biogas conditioning, biogas upgrading and biogas utilization from a safety, environmental, performance and functionality perspective, during the design, manufacturing, installation, construction, testing, commissioning, acceptance, operation, regular inspection and maintenance phases.

Biogas installations are, among others, applied at industrial plants like food and beverage industries, waste water treatment plants, waste plants, landfill sites, small scale plants next to agricultural companies and small scale household installations.

The following topics are excluded from this document:

- boilers, burners, furnaces and lightening, in case these are not specifically applied for locally produced biogas;
- gas-fuelled engines for vehicles and ships;
- the public gas grid;
- specifications to determine biomethane quality;
- transportation of compressed or liquefied biogas;

- transportation of biomass or digestate;
- assessment and determination whether biomass is sourced sustainably or not.

This document describes the following for information purposes as well:

- the parameters to determine the size (e.g. small, medium-sized, or large scale);
- the parameters to determine the type of installation (e.g. domestic, industrial);
- the parameters to describe the type of technique;
- terms and processes in order to develop health, safety and environmental protection guidelines for biogas installations.

NOTE For an explanation of the Scope, see [Annex A](#).

iv. Project of standards:

3 projects of ISO standards <https://www.iso.org/committee/617083/x/catalogue/p/0/u/1/w/0/d/0> under development, but we consider relevant for GLOMICAVE the following:

- ISO/AWI TR 23585 Safety and Environment Guidelines for Biogas
- ISO/DIS 24252 Biogas systems — Non-household and non-gasification

3.2 Information technology

Technical Committees:

1. IEC SEG 10 Ethics in Autonomous and Artificial Intelligence Applications CEN/CENELEC Focus Group on Artificial Intelligence

i. Scope:

Identify ethical issues and societal concerns relevant to IEC technical activities.
 Formulate recommendations to SMB as appropriate.
 Develop broadly applicable guidelines for IEC committees on ethical aspects related to autonomous and/or AI applications.
 Ensure work consistency across IEC committees and foster cooperation with JTC 1/SC 42.
 Consider any change needed in the IEC Use Case Template to address ethical issues and societal concerns.
 Set up relevant fora during IEC General Meetings and invite other relevant actors on this matter to participate on the discussion such as the academia.

ii. Structure: ---

iii. Standards: ---

iv. Project of standards: ---

2. ISO/IEC JTC1 Information technology

i. Scope: Standardization in the field of information technology

ii. Structure:

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 2	Coded character sets
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 6	Telecommunications and information exchange between systems
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7	Software and systems engineering
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 17	Cards and security devices for personal identification
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 22	Programming languages, their environments and system software interfaces
<u>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 23</u>	<u>Digitally recorded media for information interchange and storage</u>
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 24	Computer graphics, image processing and environmental data representation
<u>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25</u>	<u>Interconnection of information technology equipment</u>
<u>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27</u>	<u>Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection</u>
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 28	Office equipment
<u>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29</u>	<u>Coding of audio, picture, multimedia and hypermedia information</u>
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 31	Automatic identification and data capture techniques
<u>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 32</u>	<u>Data management and interchange</u>
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 34	Document description and processing languages
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 35	User interfaces
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 36	Information technology for learning, education and training
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37	Biometrics
<u>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38</u>	<u>Cloud computing and distributed platforms</u>
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 39	Sustainability, IT and data centres
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 40	IT service management and IT governance
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41	Internet of things and digital twin
<u>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42</u>	<u>Artificial intelligence</u>
ISO/IEC JTC 1/AG 1	Advisory Group on Communications
ISO/IEC JTC 1/AG 2	Advisory Group on JTC 1 Emerging Technology and Innovation (JETI)
ISO/IEC JTC 1/AG 6	Autonomous and Data Rich Vehicles
ISO/IEC JTC 1/AG 8	Meta Reference Architecture and Reference Architecture for Systems Integration
ISO/IEC JTC 1/AG 10	Outreach
ISO/IEC JTC 1/AG 12	Technical Corrigenda
ISO/IEC JTC 1/AG 13	Use Cases for VR and AR based ICT Integration Systems
ISO/IEC JTC 1/AG 14	Systems Integration Facilitation (SIF)
ISO/IEC JTC 1/AG 15	Standards and Regulations
ISO/IEC JTC 1/AG 16	Brain-computer interface
ISO/IEC JTC 1/AG 17	Meeting guidelines - SD 19
ISO/IEC JTC 1/AG 18	Vocabulary
ISO/IEC JTC 1/JAG	JTC 1 Advisory Group
ISO/IEC JTC 1/WG 11	Smart cities
ISO/IEC JTC 1/WG 12	3D Printing and scanning
ISO/IEC JTC 1/WG 13	Trustworthiness
ISO/IEC JTC 1/WG 14	Quantum Computing

All standards published by the ISO / IEC JTC1 subcommittees have been reviewed and only the relevant subcommittees for GLOMICAVE project have been underlined in the ISO / IEC JTC1 structure. The scope of these subcommittees, as well as their relevant standards and draft standards are detailed below.

a. ISO/IEC JTC1/SC23 Digitally recorded media for information interchange and storage

a.i Scope:

Standardization in the field of removable digital storage media utilizing optical, holographic and magnetic recording technologies, and flash memory technologies for digital information interchange, including;

- **algorithms** for the lossless compression of data
- volume and file structure
- methods for determining the life expectancy of digital storage media
- methods for error monitoring of digital storage media

a.ii Structure: ---

a.iii Standards:

132 published ISO standards
<https://www.iso.org/committee/45240/x/catalogue/p/1/u/0/w/0/d/0>, but we consider relevant for GLOMICAVE the following:

- ISO/IEC 11558:1992 Information technology — Data compression for information interchange — Adaptive coding with embedded dictionary — DCLZ Algorithm

Scope:

This International Standard specifies a lossless compression algorithm to reduce the number of bits required to represent information coded by means of 8-bit bytes. This algorithm is known as DCLZ (Data Compression according to Lempel and Ziv).

This International Standard specifies neither the strategy for resetting the dictionary nor that for freezing it, as these are implementation-dependent.

This algorithm is particularly useful when information has to be recorded on an inter-changeable medium. Its use is not limited to this application.

- ISO/IEC 11576:1994 Information technology — Procedure for the registration of algorithms for the lossless compression of data

Scope:

This International Standard specifies the procedure to be followed by a Registration Authority in preparing, maintaining and publishing an International Register of numeric identifiers allocated to algorithms for the lossless compression of data, excluding cryptographic algorithms.

For the purpose of this International Standard, an algorithm is a set of rules for the transformation of the coded representation of data from one form to another, which allows the lossless restitution of the original form.

An identifier registered in accordance with this International Standard serves as an identification of the algorithm associated with it in the Register. Apart from such identification, registration does not affect the status of the algorithm concerned. Thus, the registration procedure must be clearly distinguished from the standardization process.

- ISO/IEC 12042:1993 Information technology — Data compression for information interchange — Binary arithmetic coding algorithm

Scope:

This International Standard specifies an algorithm for the reduction of the number of bits required to represent information. This process is known as data compression. The algorithm uses binary arithmetic coding. The algorithm provides lossless compression and is intended for use in information interchange.

- ISO/IEC 15200:1996 Information technology — Adaptive Lossless Data Compression algorithm (ALDC)

Scope:

This International Standard specifies a lossless compression algorithm to reduce the number of bytes required to represent data. The algorithm is known as Adaptive Lossless Data Compression algorithm (ALDC). The numerical identifiers according to ISO/IEC 11576 allocated to this algorithm are:

ALDC 512-Byte History Buffer: 3

ALDC 1024-Byte History Buffer: 4

ALDC 2048-Byte History Buffer: 5

- ISO/IEC 22091:2002 Information technology — Streaming Lossless Data Compression algorithm (SLDC)

Scope:

This International Standard specifies a lossless compression algorithm to reduce the number of 8-bit bytes required to represent data records and File Marks. The algorithm is known as Streaming Lossless Data Compression algorithm (SLDC).

One buffer size (1 024 bytes) is specified.

The numerical identifier according to ISO/IEC 11576 allocated to this algorithm is 6.

a.iv Project of standards:

- ISO/IEC DIS 9660 Information processing – Volume and file structure of CD-ROM for information interchange
- ISO/IEC 30193:2020/DAMD 1 Information technology – Digitally recorded media for information interchange and storage – 120 mm Triple Layer (100,0 Gbytes per disk) DB Rewritable disk – Amendment 1

b. ISO/IEC JTC1/SC25 Interconnection of information technology equipment

b.i Scope:

Standardization of microprocessor systems, interfaces, protocols, architectures and associated interconnecting media for information technology equipment and networks to support embedded and distributed computing environments, storage systems and other input/output components.

Standards for home and building electronic systems in residential and commercial environments to support interworking devices (IoT-related) and applications such as energy management, environmental control, lighting, and security.

Cabling system standards for information and communication technology (ICT), in all types of residential, commercial and industrial environments for the design, planning and installation, test procedures, automated infrastructure management systems and remote powering.

b.ii Structure:

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25/WG 1	Home electronic systems
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25/WG 3	Customer premises cabling
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25/WG 4	Interconnection of computer systems and attached equipment

b.iii Standards:

224 published ISO standards
<https://www.iso.org/committee/45270/x/catalogue/p/1/u/0/w/0/d/0>, but we consider relevant for GLOMICAVE the following:

- ISO/IEC 11002:2008 Information technology — Multipath management API

Scope:

This International Standard provides management interfaces to standard capabilities defined in ISO/IEC 14776-453 (SPC-3) and common vendor-specific extensions to the standard capabilities. The intended audience is vendors that deliver drivers that provide these capabilities. This standard relates to SCSI multipathing features and excludes multipathing between interconnect devices (such as Fibre Channel switches) and transport specific multipathing (such as iSCSI multiple connections per session).

- ISO/IEC 14776-453:2009 Information technology – Small computer system interface (SCSI) – Part: 453: Primary commands-3 (SPC-3)

Scope:

The SCSI family of standards provides for many different types of SCSI devices (e.g., disks, tapes, printers, scanners). This standard defines a device model that is applicable to all SCSI devices. Other SCSI command standards (see 3.1.18) expand on the general SCSI device model in ways appropriate to specific types of SCSI devices.

The set of SCSI standards specifies the interfaces, functions, and operations necessary to ensure interoperability between conforming SCSI implementations. This standard is a functional description. Conforming implementations may employ any design technique that does not violate interoperability.

This standard defines the SCSI commands that are mandatory and optional for all SCSI devices. Support for any feature defined in this standard is optional unless otherwise stated. This standard also defines the SCSI commands that may apply to any device model.

The following commands, parameter data, and features defined in previous versions of this standard are made obsolete by this standard:

- a) Contingent Allegiance;
- b) Untagged tasks;
- c) The RESERVE(6) and RESERVE(10) commands;
- d) The RELEASE(6) and RELEASE(10) commands;
- e) The ELEMENT_SCOPE for Persistent Reservations;
- f) The command support data (CMDDr) feature of the INQUIRY command;
- g) The relative addressing (RELADR) bit in the standard INQUIRY data;
- h) The Medium Partition mode pages (2), (3), and (4);
- i) The Control mode page DISABLE_QUEUEING bit;
- j) Discussion of the SBC REBUILD, REGENERATE and XDWRITE EXTENDED commands; and
- k) The ASCII Implemented Operating Definition VPD page.

Figure 1 shows the relationship of this standard to the other standards and related projects in the SCSI family of standards as of the publication of this standard.

Figure 1 — SCSI document relationships

Figure 1 is intended to show the general relationship of the documents to one another. Figure 1 is not intended to imply a relationship such as a hierarchy, protocol stack, or system architecture. It indicates the applicability of a standard to the implementation of a given transport.

The term SCSI is used to refer to the family of standards described in this clause.

b.iv Project of standards:

- ISO/IEC AWI 10192-4-1 Information technology — Home electronic system (HES) interfaces — Part 4-1: Common user interface and interoperability among home systems — Architecture

- ISO/IEC AWI 24383 Information technology — Physical network security for the accommodation of customer premises cabling infrastructure and information technology equipment

c. ISO/IEC JTC1/SC27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection

c.i Scope:

The development of standards for the protection of information and ICT. This includes generic methods, techniques and guidelines to address both security and privacy aspects, such as:

Security requirements capture methodology;

Management of information and ICT security; in particular information security management systems, security processes, and security controls and services;

Cryptographic and other security mechanisms, including but not limited to mechanisms for protecting the accountability, availability, integrity and confidentiality of information;

Security management support documentation including terminology, guidelines as well as procedures for the registration of security components;

Security aspects of identity management, biometrics and privacy;

Conformance assessment, accreditation and auditing requirements in the area of information security management systems;

Security evaluation criteria and methodology.

SC 27 engages in active liaison and collaboration with appropriate bodies to ensure the proper development and application of SC 27 standards and technical reports in relevant areas.

c.ii Structure:

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/AG 1	Management Advisory Group
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/AG 2	Trustworthiness
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/AG 3	Concepts and Terminology
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/AG 4	Data security
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/AG 5	Strategy
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/AG 6	Operations
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/AG 7	Communication and Outreach (AG-CO)
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/CAG	Chair's Advisory Group
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 1	Information security management systems
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 2	Cryptography and security mechanisms
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 3	Security evaluation, testing and specification
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 4	Security controls and services
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 5	Identity management and privacy technologies

c.iii Standards:

207 published ISO standards
<https://www.iso.org/committee/45306/x/catalogue/p/1/u/0/w/0/d/0> , but we consider relevant for GLOMICAVE the following:

- ISO/IEC 18033-1:2015 Information technology — Security techniques — Encryption algorithms — Part 1: General

Scope:

This part of ISO/IEC 18033 is general in nature, and provides definitions that apply in subsequent parts of this International Standard. The nature of encryption is introduced, and certain general aspects of its use and properties are described. The criteria used to select the algorithms specified in subsequent parts of this International Standard are defined in [Annexes A and B](#).

• ISO/IEC 18033-2:2006/AMD1:2017 Information technology — Security techniques — Encryption algorithms — Part 2: Asymmetric ciphers

Scope:

This part of ISO/IEC 18033 specifies several asymmetric ciphers. These specifications prescribe the functional interfaces and correct methods of use of such ciphers in general, as well as the precise functionality and cipher text format for several specific asymmetric ciphers (although conforming systems may choose to use alternative formats for storing and transmitting cipher-texts).

A normative annex (Annex A) gives ASN.1 syntax for object identifiers, public keys, and parameter structures to be associated with the algorithms specified in this part of ISO/IEC 18033.

However, these specifications do not prescribe protocols for reliably obtaining a public key, for proof of possession of a private key, or for validation of either public or private keys; see ISO/IEC 11770-3 for guidance on such key management issues.

The asymmetric ciphers that are specified in this part of ISO/IEC 18033 are indicated in Clause 7.6.

NOTE Briefly, the asymmetric ciphers are:

- ECIES-HC; PSEC-HC; ACE-HC: generic hybrid ciphers based on ElGamal encryption;
- RSA-HC: a generic hybrid cipher based on the RSA transform;
- RSAES: the OAEP padding scheme applied to the RSA transform;
- HIME(R): a scheme based on the hardness of factoring.

• ISO/IEC 18033-3:2010 Information technology — Security techniques — Encryption algorithms — Part 3: Block ciphers

Scope:

This part of ISO/IEC 18033 specifies block ciphers. A block cipher maps blocks of n bits to blocks of n bits, under the control of a key of k bits. A total of seven different block ciphers are defined. They are categorized in Table 1.

Table 1 — Block ciphers specified

Block length	Algorithm name (see #)	Key length
64 bits	TDEA (4.2)	128 or 192 bits
	MISTY1 (4.3)	128 bits
	CAST-128 (4.4)	
	HIGHT (4.5)	
128 bits	AES (5.2)	128, 192 or 256 bits
	Camellia (5.3)	128 bits
	SEED (5.4)	

The algorithms specified in this part of ISO/IEC 18033 have been assigned object identifiers in accordance with ISO/IEC 9834. The list of assigned object identifiers is given in Annex B. Any changes to the specification of the algorithms resulting in a change of functional behaviour will result in a change of the object identifier assigned to the algorithm.

• ISO/IEC 18033-4:2011/AMD1:2020 Information technology — Security techniques — Encryption algorithms — Part 4: Stream ciphers

Scope:

This part of ISO/IEC 18033 specifies

- a) output functions to combine a keystream with plaintext,
- b) keystream generators for producing keystream, and
- c) object identifiers assigned to dedicated keystream generators in accordance with ISO/IEC 9834.

NOTE 1 The list of assigned object identifiers is given in Annex A.

NOTE 2 Any change to the specification of these algorithms resulting in a change of functional behaviour will result in a change of the object identifier assigned to the algorithms concerned.

- ISO/IEC 18033-5:2015/AMD 1:2021 Information technology — Security techniques — Encryption algorithms — Part 5: Identity-based ciphers

Scope:

This part of ISO/IEC 18033 specifies identity-based encryption mechanisms. For each mechanism the functional interface, the precise operation of the mechanism, and the ciphertext format are specified. However, conforming systems may use alternative formats for storing and transmitting ciphertexts.

- ISO/IEC 18033-6:2019 Information technology — Security techniques — Encryption algorithms — Part 6: Homomorphic encryption

Scope:

This document specifies the following mechanisms for homomorphic encryption.

- Exponential ElGamal encryption;
- Paillier encryption.

For each mechanism, this document specifies the process for:

- generating parameters and the keys of the involved entities;
- encrypting data;
- decrypting encrypted data; and
- homomorphically operating on encrypted data.

[Annex A](#) defines the object identifiers assigned to the mechanisms specified in this document. [Annex B](#) provides numerical examples.

- ISO/IEC 18367:2016 Information technology — Security techniques — Cryptographic algorithms and security mechanisms conformance testing

Scope:

This document gives guidelines for cryptographic algorithms and security mechanisms conformance testing methods.

Conformance testing assures that an implementation of a cryptographic algorithm or security mechanism is correct whether implemented in hardware, software or firmware. It also confirms that it runs correctly in a specific operating environment. Testing can consist of known-answer or Monte Carlo testing, or a combination of test methods. Testing can be performed on the actual implementation or modelled in a simulation environment.

This document does not include the efficiency of the algorithms or security mechanisms nor the intrinsic performance. This document focuses on the correctness of the implementation.

c.iv Project of standards:

- ISO/IEC DIS 20897-2 Information security, **cybersecurity** and privacy protection — Physically unclonable functions — Part 2: Test and evaluation methods

- ISO/IEC DTR 22216 Information technology — Security techniques — Introductory guidance on evaluation for IT security
- ISO/IEC CD 23837-1 Information technology security techniques — Security requirements, test and evaluation methods for quantum key distribution — Part 1: Requirements
- ISO/IEC CD 23837-2 Information technology security techniques — Security requirements, test and evaluation methods for quantum key distribution — Part 2: Evaluation and testing methods
- ISO/IEC DTR 24485.3 Information technology — Security techniques — Security properties, test and evaluation guidance for white box cryptography
- ISO/IEC CD 27400.3 **Cybersecurity** – IoT security and privacy – Guidelines
- ISO/IEC CD 29128.2 Information security — Verification of cryptographic protocols
- ISO/IEC DIS 15946-5 Information technology — Security techniques — Cryptographic techniques based on elliptic curves — Part 5: Elliptic curve generation
- ISO/IEC DIS 20009-3 Information security — Anonymous entity authentication — Part 3: Mechanisms based on blind signatures
- ISO/IEC DIS 24745 Information security, **cybersecurity** and privacy protection — Biometric information protection
- ISO/IEC DIS 27002 Information security, **cybersecurity** and privacy protection — Information security controls
- ISO/IEC DIS 27013 Information security, **cybersecurity** and privacy protection — Guidance on the integrated implementation of ISO/IEC 27001 and ISO/IEC 20000-1
- ISO/IEC DIS 27070 Information technology — Security techniques — Requirements for establishing virtualized roots of trust
- ISO/IEC DIS 27555 Information security, **cybersecurity** and privacy protection – Guidelines on personally identifiable information deletion
- ISO/IEC FDIS 27050-4 Information technology — Electronic discovery — Part 4: Technical readiness
- ISO/IEC WD 4983 Information technology — Security techniques — Remedial Systems Updating
- ISO/IEC WD 24392.4 Information technology — Security techniques — Security reference model for Industrial Internet Platform (IIP)
- ISO/IEC WD 24760-2 Information technology — Security techniques — A framework for identity management — Part 2: Reference architecture and requirements
- ISO/IEC 24760-3:2016/WD AMD 1 Information technology — Security techniques — A framework for identity management — Part 3: Practice — Amendment 1
- ISO/IEC WD 27035-4 Information technology — Information security incident management — Part 4: Coordination
- ISO/IEC WD 27036-2 Information technology — Security techniques — Information security for supplier relationships — Part 2: Requirements
- ISO/IEC WD 27045.6 Information technology — Big data security and privacy — Processes
- ISO/IEC WD 27403.3 **Cybersecurity** – IoT security and privacy – Guidelines for IoT-domotics
- ISO/IEC WD 27557.2 Information technology — Organizational privacy risk management
- ISO/IEC WD 27559.2 Privacy enhancing data de-identification framework
- ISO/IEC WD TS 27560.2 Privacy technologies — Consent record information structure
- ISO/IEC CD 4922-1 Information security — Secure multiparty computation — Part 1: General
- ISO/IEC CD 18033-7 Information technology — Security techniques — Encryption **algorithms** — Part 7: Tweakable block ciphers
- ISO/IEC CD 23264-2 Information security — Redaction of authentic data — Part 2: Redactable signature schemes based on asymmetric mechanisms
- ISO/IEC CD 27005.2 Information security, **cybersecurity** and privacy protection — Guidance on managing information security risks and opportunities
- ISO/IEC CD 27032 Information Technology — **Cybersecurity** — Guidelines for Internet Security
- ISO/IEC CD 27035-1 Information technology – Information security incident management — Part 1: Principles and process
- ISO/IEC CD 27035-2 Information technology — Information security incident management — Part 2: Guidelines to plan and prepare for incident management
- ISO/IEC CD 27099.3 Information Technology — Public key infrastructure — Practices and policy framework

- ISO/IEC CD 27402 **Cybersecurity** — IoT security and privacy — Device baseline requirements
- ISO/IEC CD 27553 Information technology — Security techniques — Security requirements for authentication using biometrics on mobile devices
- ISO/IEC CD 27556.2 Information technology — User-centric framework for the handling of personally identifiable information (PII) based on privacy preferences
- ISO/IEC 29134:2017/CD COR 1 Information technology — Security techniques — Guidelines for privacy impact assessment — Technical Corrigendum 1
- ISO/IEC CD 29192-8 Information security — Lightweight cryptography — Part 8: Authenticated encryption
- ISO/IEC DIS 9797-2 Information security — Message authentication codes (MACs) — Part 2: Mechanisms using a dedicated hash-function
- ISO/IEC DIS 11770-7 Information security — Key management — Part 7: Cross-domain password-based authenticated key exchange
- ISO/IEC DIS 18014-2 Information security — Time-stamping services — Part 2: Mechanisms producing independent tokens
- ISO/IEC DIS 18033-1 Information security — Encryption **algorithms** — Part 1: General
- ISO/IEC 18033-3:2010/DAMD 1 Information technology — Security techniques — Encryption **algorithms** — Part 3: Block ciphers — Amendment 1: SM4
- ISO/IEC 27021:2017/DAMD 1 Information technology — Security techniques — Competence requirements for information security management systems professionals — Amendment 1: Addition of ISO/IEC 27001: 2013 clauses or subclauses to competence requirements
- ISO/IEC DIS 27551 Information security, **cybersecurity** and privacy protection — Requirements for attribute-based unlinkable entity authentication
- ISO/IEC WD 27031 Information technology — Guidelines for ICT readiness for business continuity
- ISO/IEC WD 29115.4 Information technology — Security techniques — Entity authentication assurance framework
- ISO/IEC CD 20009-3 Information security — Anonymous entity authentication — Part 3: Mechanisms based on blind signatures
- ISO/IEC DTS 23532-1 Information security, **cybersecurity** and privacy protection — Requirements for the competence of IT security testing and evaluation laboratories — Part 1: Evaluation for ISO/IEC 15408
- ISO/IEC DTS 23532-2 Information security, **cybersecurity** and privacy protection — Requirements for the competence of IT security testing and evaluation laboratories — Part 2: Testing for ISO/IEC 19790
- ISO/IEC 11770-3:2015/DAMD 2 Information technology — Security techniques — Key management — Part 3: Mechanisms using asymmetric techniques — Amendment 2: SM9 key agreement protocol
- ISO/IEC 19772:2009/DAMD 1 Information technology — Security techniques — Authenticated encryption — Amendment 1
- ISO/IEC DIS 27034-4 Information technology — Security techniques — Application security — Part 4: Validation and verification
- ISO/IEC DIS 15408-1 Information security, **cybersecurity** and privacy protection — Evaluation criteria for IT security — Part 1: Vocabulary, introduction and general model
- ISO/IEC DIS 15408-2 Information security, **cybersecurity** and privacy protection — Evaluation criteria for IT security — Part 2: Security functional components
- ISO/IEC DIS 15408-3 Information security, **cybersecurity** and privacy protection — Evaluation criteria for IT security — Part 3: Security assurance components
- ISO/IEC DIS 15408-4 Information security, **cybersecurity** and privacy protection — Evaluation criteria for IT security — Part 4: Framework for the specification of evaluation methods and activities
- ISO/IEC DIS 15408-5 Information security, **cybersecurity** and privacy protection — Evaluation criteria for IT security — Part 5: Pre-defined packages of security requirements
- ISO/IEC DIS 18045 Information security, **cybersecurity** and privacy protection — Evaluation criteria for IT security — Methodology for IT security evaluation
- ISO/IEC AWI TR 6114 Information technology – Security techniques – Security assurance throughout system life cycle

- ISO/IEC AWI TR 6890 Towards creating an extension for patch management for ISO/IEC 15408 and ISO/IEC 18045
- ISO/IEC 9797-1:2011/AWI AMD 1 Information technology — Security techniques — Message Authentication Codes (MACs) — Part 1: Mechanisms using a block cipher — Amendment 1: Information technology — Security techniques — Message authentication codes (MACs) — Part 1: Mechanisms using a block cipher — Amendment 1
- ISO/IEC AWI 11770-8 Information technology — Security techniques — Key management — Part 8: Password-based key derivation
- ISO/IEC AWI 20008-3 Information technology — Security techniques — Anonymous digital signatures — Part 3: Mechanisms using multiple public keys
- ISO/IEC WD 4922-2.2 Information security — Secure multiparty computation — Part 2: Mechanisms based on secret sharing
- ISO/IEC WD 9798-5 Information technology — Security techniques — Entity authentication — Part 5: Mechanisms using zero-knowledge techniques
- ISO/IEC WD 14888-4 Information technology — Security techniques — Digital signatures with appendix — Part 4: Stateful hash-based mechanisms
- ISO/IEC WD 17825 Information technology — Security techniques — Testing methods for the mitigation of non-invasive attack classes against cryptographic modules
- ISO/IEC WD 18031 Information technology — Security techniques — Random bit generation
- ISO/IEC WD 19790 Information technology — Security techniques — Security requirements for cryptographic modules
- ISO/IEC 20008-2:2013/WD AMD 2 Information technology — Security techniques — Anonymous digital signatures — Part 2: Mechanisms using a group public key — Amendment 2
- ISO/IEC WD 24759 Information technology — Security techniques — Test requirements for cryptographic modules
- ISO/IEC WD 27011.4 Information technology — Security techniques — Code of practice for Information security controls based on ISO/IEC 27002 for telecommunications organizations
- ISO/IEC WD 27031 Information technology — **Cybersecurity** — Information and communication technology readiness for business continuity
- ISO/IEC WD 27033-7 Information technology – Network security — Part 7: Guidelines for network virtualization security
- ISO/IEC WD 27040.2 Information technology — Security techniques — Storage security
- ISO/IEC WD 27046.2 Information technology — Big data security and privacy — Implementation guidelines
- ISO/IEC WD 27071.4 Information technology – Security techniques – Security recommendations for establishing trusted connections between devices and services
- ISO/IEC WD 27554.3 Application of ISO 31000 for assessment of identity management-related risk

d. ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29 Coding of audio, picture, multimedia and hypermedia information

d.i Scope:

Standardization in the field of

- Efficient coding of digital representations of images, audio and moving pictures, including
 - Conventional (natural, computer-generated and immersive) images, moving pictures and audio
 - Invisible light and other sensory (such as medical and satellite) images
 - Static and dynamic graphic objects
- Efficient coding of other digital information, including
 - Multimedia, environment and user related metadata
 - Sensor and actuator information related to audiovisual information
 - Other digital data in agreement with the relevant committee, such as genomics
- Digital information support, including
 - Synchronization, presentation, storage and transport of single or combinations of media

- Media security and privacy management
- Quality of Experience evaluation and system performance metrics

d.ii Structure:

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/AG 1	Chair Support Team and Management
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/AG 2	MPEG Technical coordination
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/AG 3	MPEG Liaison and communication
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/AG 4	JPEG and MPEG Collaboration
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/AG 5	MPEG Visual quality assessment
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/WG 1	JPEG Coding of digital representations of images
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/WG 2	MPEG Technical requirements
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/WG 3	MPEG Systems
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/WG 4	MPEG Video coding
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/WG 5	MPEG Joint Video Coding Team(s) with ITU-T SG 16
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/WG 6	MPEG Audio coding
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/WG 7	MPEG 3D Graphics coding
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/WG 8	MPEG Genomic coding

d.iii Standards:

580 published ISO standards
<https://www.iso.org/committee/45316/x/catalogue/p/1/u/0/w/0/d/0>, but we consider relevant for GLOMICAVE the following:

- ISO/IEC 23092-1:2020 Information technology – Genomic information representation – Part 1: Transport and storage of genomic information

Scope:

This document specifies data formats for both transport and storage of genomic information, including the conversion process.

- ISO/IEC 23092-2:2020 Information technology – Genomic information representation – Part 2: Coding of genomic information

Scope:

This document provides specifications for the normative representation of the following types of genomic information:

- unaligned sequencing reads including read identifiers and quality values;
- aligned sequencing reads including read identifiers and quality values;
- reference sequences.

- ISO/IEC 23092-3:2020 Information technology – Genomic information representation – Part 3: Metadata and application programming interfaces (APIs)

Scope:

This document specifies information metadata, auxiliary fields, SAM interoperability, protection metadata and programming interfaces of genomic information. It defines:

- metadata storage and interpretation for the different encapsulation levels as specified in ISO/IEC 23092-1 (in **Clause 6**);
- protection elements providing confidentiality, integrity and privacy rules at the different encapsulation levels specified in ISO/IEC 23092-1 (in **Clause 7**);
- how to associate auxiliary fields to encoded reads (in **Clause 8**);
- mechanisms for backward compatibility with existing SAM content, and exportation to this format (in **Annex C**);
- interfaces to access genomic information coded in compliance with ISO/IEC 23092-1 and ISO/IEC 23092-2 (in subclause **8.1**).

- ISO/IEC 23092-4:2020 Information technology – Genomic information representation – Part 4: Reference software

Scope:

This document specifies genomic information representation reference software, referred to as the genomic model (GM). This decoding software is provided to assess conformance to the requirements of ISO/IEC 23092-1 and ISO/IEC 23092-2.

- ISO/IEC 23092-5:2020 Information technology – Genomic information representation – Part 5: Conformance

Scope:

This document specifies a set of test procedures designed to verify whether bitstreams and decoders meet requirements specified in ISO/IEC 23092-1 and ISO/IEC 23092-2.

Procedures are described for testing conformity of bitstreams and decoders to the requirements that are fully determined in ISO/IEC 23092-1 and ISO/IEC 23092-2. This document identifies those requirements, associates them to functionality under test and defines how conformity with them can be tested. Test bitstreams implemented according to those functionalities are provided in electronic form.

d.iv Project of standards:

- ISO/IEC AWI TR 23009-3 Information technology — Dynamic adaptive streaming over HTTP (DASH) — Part 3: Implementation guidelines
- ISO/IEC AWI 6048 JPEG AI Learning-based Image Coding System
- ISO/IEC 14496-10:2020/AWI Amd 1 Information technology — Coding of audio-visual objects — Part 10: Advanced video coding — Amendment 1: Additional SEI messages
- ISO/IEC 14496-22:2019/AWI Amd 2 Information technology — Coding of audio-visual objects — Part 22: Open Font Format — Amendment 2: Extending color font functionality and other updates
- ISO/IEC AWI 19566-8 Information technologies — JPEG systems — Part 8: JPEG Snack
- ISO/IEC AWI 23001-17 Information technology — MPEG systems technologies — Part 17: Carriage of Uncompressed video in the ISO base media file format
- ISO/IEC 23002-7:2021/AWI Amd 1 Information technology — MPEG video technologies — Part 7: Versatile supplemental enhancement information messages for coded video bitstreams — Amendment 1: Additional SEI messages
- ISO/IEC 23090-3/AWI Amd 1 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 3: Versatile video coding — Amendment 1: Operation range extensions
- ISO/IEC WD 15444-8 Information technology — JPEG 2000 image coding system — Part 8: Secure JPEG 2000
- ISO/IEC WD 15444-9 Information technology — JPEG 2000 image coding system — Part 9: Interactivity tools, APIs and protocols
- ISO/IEC WD 15444-17 Information technology — JPEG 2000 image coding system — Part 17: Extensions for coding of discontinuous media
- ISO/IEC WD 18181-3 Information technology — JPEG XL Image Coding System — Part 3: Conformance testing
- ISO/IEC WD TR 23009-7 Information technology — Dynamic adaptive streaming over HTTP (DASH) — Part 7: Delivery of CMAF contents with DASH
- ISO/IEC WD 23090-11 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 11: Network-based media processing implementation guidelines
- ISO/IEC WD 23090-13 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 13: Video Decoding Interface for Immersive Media
- ISO/IEC WD 23094-3 Information technology — General video coding — Part 3: Conformance and Reference Software for Low Complexity Enhancement Video Coding
- ISO/IEC 21122-1:2019/WD Amd 1 Information technology — JPEG XS low-latency lightweight image coding system — Part 1: Core coding system — Amendment 1: Extended capabilities for JPEG XS core coding system
- ISO/IEC 21122-2:2019/AWI Amd 1 Information technology — JPEG XS low-latency lightweight image coding system — Part 2: Profiles and buffer models — Amendment 1: Profiles extensions
- ISO/IEC 14496-26:2010/WD Amd 6 Information technology — Coding of audio-visual objects — Part 26: Audio conformance — Amendment 6: Conformance for New levels of MPEG-4 ALS simple profile for supporting high-resolution audio

- ISO/IEC WD 21122-4 Information technology — JPEG XS low-latency lightweight image coding system — Part 4: Conformance testing
- ISO/IEC WD 21122-5 Information technology — JPEG XS low-latency lightweight image coding system — Part 5: Reference software
- ISO/IEC 14496-15:2019/CD Amd 3 Information technology — Coding of audio-visual objects — Part 15: Carriage of network abstraction layer (NAL) unit structured video in the ISO base media file format — Amendment 3: Support for LCEVC
- ISO/IEC 14496-30:2018/CD Amd 1 Information technology — Coding of audio-visual objects — Part 30: Timed text and other visual overlays in ISO base media file format — Amendment 1: Timing improvements
- ISO/IEC CD 18181-4 Information technology — JPEG XL Image Coding System — Part 4: Reference software
- ISO/IEC CD 21000-23 Information technology — Multimedia framework (MPEG-21) - — Part 23: MPEG IPR Smart Contracts
- ISO/IEC 23000-19:2020/CD Amd 2 Information technology — Multimedia application format (MPEG-A) — Part 19: Common media application format (CMAF) for segmented media — Amendment 2: CMAF Media Profiles for MPEG-H 3D Audio, EVC, VVC and other technologies
- ISO/IEC 23001-7:2016/CD Amd 2 Information technology — MPEG systems technologies — Part 7: Common encryption in ISO base media file format files — Amendment 2: Improvements on selective encryption
- ISO/IEC CD 23001-18 Information technology — MPEG systems technologies — Part 18: EventMessage tracks in the ISO base media file format
- ISO/IEC CD 23003-6 Information technology — MPEG audio technologies — Part 6: Unified speech and audio coding reference software
- ISO/IEC 23009-1:2019/CD Amd 2 Information technology — Dynamic adaptive streaming over HTTP (DASH) — Part 1: Media presentation description and segment formats — Amendment 2: Preroll, nonlinear playback and other extensions
- ISO/IEC DIS 23090-6/CD Amd 1 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 6: Immersive media metrics — Amendment 1: Immersive media metrics for V3C Data and OMAF
- ISO/IEC CD 23090-7 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 7: Immersive media metadata
- ISO/IEC CD 23090-14 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 14: Scene Description for MPEG Media
- ISO/IEC CD 23090-20 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 20: Conformance for V-PCC
- ISO/IEC CD 23090-21 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 21: Reference Software for G-PCC
- ISO/IEC CD 23090-22 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 22: Conformance for G-PCC
- ISO/IEC 23091-3:2018/CD Amd 1 Information technology — Coding-independent code points — Part 3: Audio — Amendment 1: Headphone support
- ISO/IEC 13818-1:2019/CD Amd 4 Information technology — Generic coding of moving pictures and associated audio information — Part 1: Systems — Amendment 4: Carriage of LCEVC in MPEG-2 TS and other improvements
- ISO/IEC CD TR 14496-24 Information technology — Coding of audio-visual objects — Part 24: Audio and systems interaction
- ISO/IEC DIS 18181-1/CD Amd 1 Information technology — JPEG XL Image Coding System — Part 1: Core coding system — Amendment 1: Profiles and levels for JPEG XL image coding system
- ISO/IEC CD 19566-7 Information technologies — JPEG systems — Part 7: JPEG linked media format (JLINK)
- ISO/IEC CD 23008-7 Information technology — High efficiency coding and media delivery in heterogeneous environments — Part 7: MMT Conformance

- ISO/IEC CD 23090-15 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 15: Conformance testing for versatile video coding
- ISO/IEC CD 23090-16 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 16: Reference software for versatile video coding
- ISO/IEC CD 23090-19 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 19: Reference Software for V-PCC
- ISO/IEC CD 23092-6 Information technology — **Genomic** information representation — Part 6: Coding of genomic annotations
- ISO/IEC 21122-3:2019/CD Cor 1 Information technology — JPEG XS low-latency lightweight image coding system — Part 3: Transport and container formats — Technical Corrigendum 1
- ISO/IEC 23008-4:2020/CD Amd 2 Information technology — High efficiency coding and media delivery in heterogeneous environments — Part 4: MMT reference software — Amendment 2: Information technology — High efficiency coding and media delivery in heterogeneous environments — Part 4: MMT reference and conformance software — Amendment 2: Support for MMTP extensions
- ISO/IEC CD TR 23090-1 Information technology - Coded representation of immersive media — Part 1: Immersive media
- ISO/IEC DIS 21122-2 Information technology — JPEG XS low-latency lightweight image coding system — Part 2: Profiles and buffer models
- ISO/IEC 23003-3:2020/DAMd 1 Information technology — MPEG audio technologies — Part 3: Unified speech and audio coding — Amendment 1: Reference software and conformance
- ISO/IEC DIS 23003-7 Information technology — MPEG audio technologies — Part 7: Unified speech and audio coding conformance testing
- ISO/IEC 23008-12:2017/DAMd 2 Information technology — High efficiency coding and media delivery in heterogeneous environments — Part 12: Image File Format — Amendment 2: Support for VVC, EVC, slideshows and other improvements
- ISO/IEC DIS 23090-12 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 12: Immersive Video
- ISO/IEC DIS 23093-1 Information technology — Internet of media things — Part 1: Architecture
- ISO/IEC DIS 10918-7 Information technology — Digital compression and coding of continuous-tone still images — Part 7: Reference software
- ISO/IEC 13818-1:2019/DAMd 3 Information technology — Generic coding of moving pictures and associated audio information — Part 1: Systems — Amendment 3: Carriage of EVC in MPEG-2 Systems and update of the MPEG-H 3D Audio descriptor
- ISO/IEC 14496-12:2020/DAMd 1 Information technology — Coding of audio-visual objects — Part 12: ISO base media file format — Amendment 1: Support for new media types (haptics, volumetric visual) and other improvements
- ISO/IEC DIS 15444-2 Information technology — JPEG 2000 image coding system — Part 2: Extensions
- ISO/IEC DIS 15938-17 Information technology — Multimedia content description interface — Part 17: Compression of neural networks for multimedia content description and analysis
- ISO/IEC DIS 21000-22 Information technology — Multimedia framework (MPEG-21) — Part 22: User Description
- ISO/IEC DIS 21122-1 Information technology — JPEG XS low-latency lightweight image coding system — Part 1: Core coding system
- ISO/IEC DIS 21122-3 Information technology — JPEG XS low-latency lightweight image coding system — Part 3: Transport and container formats
- ISO/IEC FDIS 21794-2/DAMd 1 Information technology — Plenoptic image coding system (JPEG Pleno) — Part 2: Light field coding — Amendment 1: Profiles and Levels for JPEG Pleno Light Field Coding System
- ISO/IEC DIS 21794-3 Information technology — Plenoptic image coding system (JPEG Pleno) — Part 3: Conformance testing
- ISO/IEC DIS 21794-4 Information technology — Plenoptic image coding system (JPEG Pleno) — Part 4: Reference software

- ISO/IEC 23000-22:2019/DAmD 2 Information technology — Multimedia application format (MPEG-A) — Part 22: Multi-image application format (MIAF) — Amendment 2: HEVC Advanced HDR profile and other clarifications
- ISO/IEC 23001-14:2019/DAmD 1 Information technology — MPEG systems technologies — Part 14: Partial file format — Amendment 1: Support for HTTP entities, enhanced file type and byte-range priorities
- ISO/IEC DIS 23001-16 Information technology — MPEG systems technologies — Part 16: Derived visual tracks in the ISO base media file format
- ISO/IEC DIS 23008-1/DAmD 2 Information technology — High efficiency coding and media delivery in heterogeneous environments — Part 1: MPEG media transport (MMT) — Amendment 2: Carriage of EVC in MMT
- ISO/IEC DIS 23008-6 Information technology — High efficiency coding and media delivery in heterogeneous environments — Part 6: 3D audio reference software
- ISO/IEC DIS 23008-9 Information technology — High efficiency coding and media delivery in heterogeneous environments — Part 9: 3D Audio conformance testing
- ISO/IEC 23090-8:2020/DAmD 1 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 8: Network based media processing — Amendment 1: NBMP function templates
- ISO/IEC DIS 23090-18 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 18: Carriage of Geometry-based Point Cloud Compression Data
- ISO/IEC DIS 23091-2 Information technology — Coding-independent code points — Part 2: Video
- ISO/IEC DIS 23093-2 Information technology — Internet of media things — Part 2: Discovery and communication **API**
- ISO/IEC DIS 23093-3 Information technology — Internet of media things — Part 3: Media data formats and **APIs**
- ISO/IEC DIS 23094-4 Information technology — General video coding — Part 4: Conformance and Reference software for Essential Video Coding
- ISO/IEC 13818-1:2019/DAmD 2 Information technology — Generic coding of moving pictures and associated audio information — Part 1: Systems — Amendment 2: Carriage of VVC in MPEG-2 Systems
- ISO/IEC 14496-15:2019/DAmD 2 Information technology — Coding of audio-visual objects — Part 15: Carriage of network abstraction layer (NAL) unit structured video in the ISO base media file format — Amendment 2: Carriage of VVC and EVC in ISO/BMFF
- ISO/IEC DIS 18181-1 Information technology — JPEG XL Image Coding System — Part 1: Core coding system
- ISO/IEC DIS 18181-2 Information technology — JPEG XL Image coding system — Part 2: File format
- ISO/IEC 19566-5:2019/DAmD 1 Information technologies — JPEG systems — Part 5: JPEG universal metadata box format (JUMBF) — Amendment 1: Support for embedding mixed codestreams
- ISO/IEC 19566-6:2019/DAmD 1 Information technologies — JPEG systems — Part 6: JPEG 360 — Amendment 1: Addition of new JPEG 360 image types and accelerated ROI rendering
- ISO/IEC 23001-10:2020/DAmD 1 Information technology — MPEG systems technologies — Part 10: Carriage of timed metadata metrics of media in ISO base media file format — Amendment 1: Support for content-guided transcoding and spatial relationship of immersive media
- ISO/IEC 23008-2:2020/DAmD 1 Information technology — High efficiency coding and media delivery in heterogeneous environments — Part 2: High efficiency video coding — Amendment 1: Shutter interval information SEI message
- ISO/IEC 23008-10:2015/DAmD 1 Information technology — High efficiency coding and media delivery in heterogeneous environments — Part 10: MPEG media transport forward error correction (FEC) codes — Amendment 1: Window-based FEC code

- ISO/IEC 23009-1:2019/DAMd 1 Information technology — Dynamic adaptive streaming over HTTP (DASH) — Part 1: Media presentation description and segment formats — Amendment 1: CMAF support, events processing model and other extensions
- ISO/IEC DIS 23009-8 Information technology — Dynamic adaptive streaming over HTTP (DASH) — Part 8: Session-based DASH operations
- ISO/IEC DIS 23090-9 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 9: Geometry-based point cloud compression
- ISO/IEC DIS 23090-10 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 10: Carriage of visual volumetric video-based coding data
- ISO/IEC DIS 23090-17 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 17: Reference software and conformance for OMAF
- ISO/IEC FDIS 14496-12/DAMd 4 Information technology — Coding of audio-visual objects — Part 12: ISO base media file format — Amendment 4: Compact movie fragments
- ISO/IEC 15444-4:2004/DAMd 1 Information technology — JPEG 2000 image coding system: Conformance testing — Part 4: — Amendment 1: High-throughput JPEG 2000 conformance testing
- ISO/IEC 15444-5:2015/DAMd 1 Information technology — JPEG 2000 image coding system: Reference software — Part 5: — Amendment 1: Additional reference software for HTJ2K
- ISO/IEC 23008-11:2015/DAMd 1 Information technology — High efficiency coding and media delivery in heterogeneous environments — Part 11: MPEG media transport composition information — Amendment 1: Customization in composition information
- ISO/IEC DIS 14496-16 Information technology — Coding of audio-visual objects — Part 16: Animation Framework eXtension (AFX)
- ISO/IEC DIS 14496-27 Information technology — Coding of audio-visual objects — Part 27: 3D Graphics conformance
- ISO/IEC DIS 15444-16 Information technology — JPEG 2000 image coding system — Part 16: Encapsulation of JPEG 2000 images into ISO/IEC 23008-12
- ISO/IEC DIS 23008-1 Information technology — High efficiency coding and media delivery in heterogeneous environments — Part 1: MPEG media transport (MMT)
- ISO/IEC DIS 23008-1/DAMd 1 Information technology — High efficiency coding and media delivery in heterogeneous environments — Part 1: MPEG media transport (MMT) — Amendment 1: Support of FCAST
- ISO/IEC DIS 23090-6 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 6: Immersive media metrics
- ISO/IEC DIS 23094-2 Information technology – General video coding — Part 2: Low complexity enhancement video coding
- ISO/IEC FDIS 15444-4 Information technology — JPEG 2000 image coding system — Part 4: Conformance Testing
- ISO/IEC FDIS 15938-16 Information technology — Multimedia content description interface — Part 16: Conformance and reference software for compact descriptors for video analysis
- ISO/IEC 23000-21:2019/FDAMd 1 Information technology — Multimedia application format (MPEG-A) — Part 21: Visual identity management application format — Amendment 1: Conformance and reference software
- ISO/IEC PRF TR 23002-8 Information technology — MPEG video technologies — Part 8: Working practices using objective metrics for evaluation of video coding efficiency experiments
- ISO/IEC FDIS 23090-2 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 2: Omnidirectional media format
- ISO/IEC PRF TR 23091-4 Information technology — Coding-independent code points — Part 4: Usage of video signal type code points
- ISO/IEC 23000-19:2020/FDAMd 1 Information technology — Multimedia application format (MPEG-A) — Part 19: Common media application format (CMAF) for segmented media — Amendment 1: Additional CMAF HEVC media profiles

- ISO/IEC FDIS 23090-5 Information technology — Coded representation of immersive media — Part 5: Visual Volumetric Video-based Coding (V3C) and Video-based Point Cloud Compression (V-PCC)
- ISO/IEC FDIS 15444-5 Information technology — JPEG 2000 image coding system — Part 5: Reference software
- ISO/IEC FDIS 21794-2 Information technology — Plenoptic image coding system (JPEG Pleno) — Part 2: Light field coding

e. ISO/IEC JTC1/SC32 Data management and interchange

e.i Scope:

Standards for data management within and among local and distributed information systems environments. SC 32 provides enabling technologies to promote harmonization of data management facilities across sector-specific areas. Specifically, SC 32 standards include:

- reference models and frameworks for the coordination of existing and emerging standards;
- definition of data domains, data types, and data structures, and their associated semantics;
- languages, services, and protocols for persistent storage, concurrent access, concurrent update, and interchange of data;
- methods, languages, services, and protocols to structure, organize, and register metadata and other information resources associated with sharing and interoperability, including electronic commerce.

e.ii Structure:

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 32/WG 1	eBusiness
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 32/WG 2	MetaData
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 32/WG 3	Database language
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 32/WG 6	Data usage

e.iii Standards:

95 published ISO standards
<https://www.iso.org/committee/45342/x/catalogue/p/1/u/0/w/0/d/0>, but we consider relevant for GLOMICAVE the following:

- ISO/IEC 20944-1:2013 Information technology – Metadata Registries Interoperability and Binding (MDR-IB) – Part 1: Framework, common vocabulary, and common provisions for conformance

Scope:

ISO/IEC 20944 is a series of International Standards that describe codings, APIs, and protocols for interacting with an ISO/IEC 11179 metadata registry (MDR).

This part of ISO/IEC 20944 provides the overview, framework, common vocabulary, and common provisions for conformance for ISO/IEC 20944. It addresses the following data interoperability features¹:

- a common framework for variety control: harmonized concepts for conforming implementations and strictly conforming implementations;
- harmonized provisions, such as mandatory requirements² and optional requirements³, and their consistent application across all bindings of ISO/IEC 20944;
- harmonized and consistent treatment of data elements with varying data obligation attributes (e.g., mandatory, conditional, optional, extended) and varying data longevity attributes (e.g., in-use, obsolete, reserved, etc.).

This part of ISO/IEC 20944 also includes a rationale that guided its development. The rationale also discusses the harmonized use of profiles (e.g., subsets, supersets, changes, etc.) of the data structure and data elements.

- ISO/IEC 20944-2:2013 Information technology – Metadata Registries Interoperability and Binding (MDR-IB) – Part 2: Coding bindings

Scope:

The ISO/IEC 20944 series of International Standards describes codings, application programming interfaces (APIs), and protocols for interacting with an ISO/IEC 11179 metadata registry (MDR).

This part of ISO/IEC 20944 specifies provisions that are common across coding bindings for the ISO/IEC 20944 series. This part of ISO/IEC 20944 includes the individual coding bindings themselves.

- ISO/IEC 20944-3:2013 Information technology – Metadata Registries Interoperability and Binding (MDR-IB) – Part 3: API bindings

Scope:

The ISO/IEC 20944 series of International Standards describes codings, application programming interfaces (APIs), and protocols for interacting with an ISO/IEC 11179 metadata registry (MDR).

This part of ISO/IEC 20944 specifies provisions that are common across API bindings for the ISO/IEC 20944 series of International Standards, and provides the individual API bindings themselves.

- ISO/IEC 20944-4:2013 Information technology – Metadata Registries Interoperability and Binding (MDR-IB) – Part 4: Protocol bindings

Scope:

The ISO/IEC 20944 series of International Standards describe codings, application programming interfaces (APIs), and protocols for interacting with an ISO/IEC 11179 metadata registry (MDR).

This part of ISO/IEC 20944 specifies provisions that are common across protocol bindings for the ISO/IEC 20944 series of International Standards, and provides the individual protocol bindings themselves.

- ISO/IEC 20944-5:2013 Information technology – Metadata Registries Interoperability and Binding (MDR-IB) – Part 5: Profiles

Scope:

The ISO/IEC 20944 series of International Standards describe codings, application programming interfaces (APIs), and protocols for interacting with an ISO/IEC 11179 metadata registry (MDR).

This part of ISO/IEC 20944 specifies the common provisions for profiles using the ISO/IEC 20944 series.

This part of ISO/IEC 20944 specifies mapping of metamodel attributes, as specified in ISO/IEC 11179-3, to identifiers for the purpose of navigating metadata registries.

e.iv Project of standards:

- ISO/IEC AWI 5207 Information technology — Data usage — Terminology and use cases
- ISO/IEC WD 5212 Information technology — Data usage — Guidance for data usage
- ISO/IEC AWI 5394 Information technology — Criteria for concept systems
- ISO/IEC AWI 6523-1 Information technology — Structure for the identification of organizations and organization parts — Part 1: Identification of organization identification schemes
- ISO/IEC AWI 6523-2 Information technology — Structure for the identification of organizations and organization parts — Part 2: Registration of organization identification schemes
- ISO/IEC AWI 11179-6 Information technology — Metadata registries (MDR) — Part 6: Registration
- ISO/IEC AWI 11179-33 Information technology — Metadata registries (MDR) — Part 33: Metamodel for data set registration
- ISO/IEC AWI 11179-34 Information technology — Metadata registries (MDR) — Part 34: Metamodel for computable object registration
- ISO/IEC AWI TR 19583-25 Information technology — Concepts and usage of metadata — Part 25: 11179-3:2013 Metamodel in XML
- ISO/IEC WD 39075 Information Technology — Database Languages — GQL
- ISO/IEC CD 11179-3.3 Information technology — Metadata registries (MDR) — Part 3: Metamodel for registry common facilities
- ISO/IEC CD 11179-31.2 Information technology — Metadata registries (MDR) — Part 31: Metamodel for data specification registration
- ISO/IEC CD 11179-32.3 Information technology — Metadata registries (MDR) — Part 32: Metamodel for concept system registration
- ISO/IEC CD 11179-35 Information technology — Metadata registries (MDR) — Part 35: Metamodel for model registration
- ISO/IEC CD TR 19583-21.2 Information technology — Concepts and usage of metadata — Part 21: 11179-3 Data model in SQL
- ISO/IEC CD 9075-1 Information technology — Database languages — SQL — Part 1: Framework (SQL/Framework)
- ISO/IEC CD 9075-2 Information technology — Database languages — SQL — Part 2: Foundation (SQL/Foundation)
- ISO/IEC CD 9075-4 Information technology — Database languages — SQL — Part 4: Persistent stored modules (SQL/PSM)
- ISO/IEC CD 9075-11 Information technology — Database languages — SQL — Part 11: Information and definition schemas (SQL/Schemata)
- ISO/IEC CD 9075-14 Information technology — Database languages — SQL — Part 14: XML-Related Specifications (SQL/XML)
- ISO/IEC CD 9075-16 Information technology — Database languages SQL — Part 16: SQL Property Graph Queries (SQL/PGQ)
- ISO/IEC CD 11179-1 Information technology — Metadata registries (MDR) — Part 1: Framework
- ISO/IEC DTR 19583-24 Information technology — Concepts and usage of metadata — Part 24: 11179-3:2013 Metamodel in RDF
- ISO/IEC CD 21838-3 Information technology — Top-level ontologies — Part 3: Descriptive ontology for linguistic and cognitive engineering (DOLCE)
- ISO/IEC CD 21838-4 Information technology — Top-level ontologies — Part 4: TUpper
- ISO/IEC CD TR 19075-6 Information technology database languages — SQL technical reports — Part 6: SQL support for JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)
- ISO/IEC CD 11179-30 Information technology — Metadata registries (MDR) — Part 30: Basic attributes of metadata
- ISO/IEC CD 15944-17 Information technology — Business operational view — Part 17: Fundamental principles and rules governing Privacy-by-Design (PbD) requirements in EDI and collaboration space context

- ISO/IEC CD 15944-18 Information technology — Business operational view — Part 18: Common principles for identification and rules for use of identifiers in business transaction
- ISO/IEC CD 15944-19 Information technology — Business operational view — Part 19: Open-edi, jurisdictional domains, and cross-border data flows (CBDF)
- ISO/IEC DIS 15944-16 Information technology — Business operational view — Part 16: Consolidated set of the rules and guidelines identified in ISO/IEC 15944 Business Operational View standards and their IT-enablement
- ISO/IEC DIS 15944-21 Information technology — Business operational view — Part 21: Application of Open-edi business transaction ontology in distributed business transaction repositories
- ISO/IEC DIS 19763-16 Information technology — Metamodel framework for **interoperability** (MFI) — Part 16: Metamodel for document model registration
- ISO/IEC DIS 19075-1 Information technology — Guidance for the use of database language SQL — Part 1: XQuery regular expressions
- ISO/IEC DIS 19075-2 Information technology — Guidance for the use of database language SQL — Part 2: Time-related information
- ISO/IEC DIS 19075-3 Information technology — Guidance for the use of database language SQL — Part 3: SQL embedded in programs using the Java™ programming language
- ISO/IEC DIS 19075-4 Information technology — Guidance for the use of database language SQL — Part 4: Routines and types using the Java™ programming language
- ISO/IEC DIS 19075-5 Information technology — Guidance for the use of database language SQL — Part 5: Row pattern recognition
- ISO/IEC DIS 19075-6 Information technology — Guidance for the use of database language SQL — Part 6: Support for JSON
- ISO/IEC DIS 19075-7 Information technology — Guidance for the use of database language SQL — Part 7: Polymorphic table functions
- ISO/IEC DIS 19075-8 Information technology — Guidance for the use of database language SQL — Part 8: Multidimensional arrays
- ISO/IEC DIS 15944-5 Information technology — Business operational view — Part 5: Identification and referencing of requirements of jurisdictional domains as sources of external constraints
- ISO/IEC DIS 15944-7 Information technology — Business operational view — Part 7: e-Business vocabulary
- ISO/IEC DIS 5218 Information technology — Codes for the representation of human sexes
- ISO/IEC DIS 15944-1 Information technology — Business operational view — Part 1: Operational aspects of open-edi for implementation
- ISO/IEC DIS 15944-8 Information technology — Business operational view — Part 8: Identification of privacy protection requirements as external constraints on business transactions
- ISO/IEC DIS 15944-9 Information technology — Business operational view — Part 9: Business transaction traceability framework for commitment exchange
- ISO/IEC DIS 15944-10 Information technology — Business operational view — Part 10: IT-enabled coded domains as semantic components in business transactions
- ISO/IEC PRF 21838-2.2 Information technology — Top-level ontologies (TLO) — Part 2: Basic Formal Ontology (BFO)
- ISO/IEC PRF 21838-1 Information technology — Top-level ontologies (TLO) — Part 1: Requirements

f. ISO/IEC JTC1/SC38 Cloud computing and distributed platforms

f.i Scope:

Standardization in the areas of Cloud Computing and Distributed Platforms including:

- Foundational concepts and technologies,
- Operational issues, and
- Interactions among Cloud Computing systems and with other distributed systems

SC 38 serves as the focus, proponent, and systems integration entity on Cloud Computing, Distributed Platforms, and the application of these technologies. SC 38 provides guidance to JTC 1, IEC, ISO and other entities developing standards in these areas.

f.ii Structure:

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/AG 1	Communications committee
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/AG 2	JTC1/SC38 Officers group
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/AG 3	Multi-cloud
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/AG 4	Cloud service connectivity
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/AG 5	Long-term strategy
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/CG 1	Liaison coordination group for JTC1/SC27
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/CG 2	Liaison coordination group for JTC1/SC41
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/CG 3	Liaison coordination group for JTC1/SC42
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/CG 4	Liaison coordination group for JTC 1/SC 7
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/CG 5	Liaison coordination group for JTC 1/WG 13
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/WG 3	Cloud Computing Fundamentals (CCF)
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/WG 5	Data in cloud computing and related technologies

f.iii Standards:

22 published ISO standards
<https://www.iso.org/committee/601355/x/catalogue/p/1/u/0/w/0/d/0>, but we consider relevant for GLOMICAVE the following:

- ISO/IEC 19941:2017 Information technology – Cloud computing – Interoperability and portability

Scope:

This document specifies cloud computing interoperability and portability types, the relationship and interactions between these two cross-cutting aspects of cloud computing and common terminology and concepts used to discuss interoperability and portability, particularly relating to cloud services.

This document is related to other standards, namely, ISO/IEC 17788, ISO/IEC 17789, ISO/IEC 19086-1, ISO/IEC 19944, and in particular, references the cross-cutting aspects and components identified in ISO/IEC 17788 and ISO/IEC 17789 respectively.

The goal of this document is to ensure that all parties involved in cloud computing, particularly CSCs, CSPs and cloud service partners (CSNs) acting as cloud service developers, have a common understanding of interoperability and portability for their specific needs. This common understanding helps to achieve interoperability and portability in cloud computing by establishing common terminology and concepts.

- ISO/IEC 22123-1:2021 Information technology – Cloud computing – Part 1: Vocabulary

Scope:

This document provides terms and definitions for vocabulary used in the field of cloud computing.

- ISO/IEC 23167:2020 Information technology – Cloud computing – Common technologies and techniques

Scope:

This document provides a description of a set of common technologies and techniques used in conjunction with cloud computing. These include:

- virtual machines (VMs) and hypervisors;
- containers and container management systems (CMSs);
- serverless computing;
- microservices architecture;
- automation;
- platform as a service systems and architecture;
- storage services;
- security, scalability and networking as applied to the above cloud computing technologies.

f.iv Project of standards:

- ISO/IEC WD TR 3445 Information technology - Cloud computing - Audit of cloud services
- ISO/IEC WD 5140 Information technology — Cloud computing — Concepts for multi-cloud and other interoperation of multiple cloud services
- ISO/IEC AWI TS 5928 Information technology — Cloud computing and distributed platforms — Modern platforms taxonomy
- ISO/IEC CD 19944-2 Cloud computing and distributed platforms — Data flow, data categories and data use — Part 2: Guidance on application and extensibility
- ISO/IEC CD 22123-2.3 Information technology — Cloud computing — Part 2: Concepts
- ISO/IEC CD 23751 Information technology — Cloud computing and distributed platforms — Data sharing agreement (DSA) framework

g. ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 Artificial intelligence

g.i Scope:

Standardization in the area of Artificial Intelligence

- Serve as the focus and proponent for JTC 1's standardization program on Artificial Intelligence
- Provide guidance to JTC 1, IEC, and ISO committees developing Artificial Intelligence applications

g.ii Structure:

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/AG 2	AI Systems Engineering
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/AHG 1	Dissemination and outreach
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/AHG 2	Liaison with SC 38
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/JWG 1	Joint Working Group ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 42 - ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 40: Governance implications of AI
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/WG 1	Foundational standards
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/WG 2	Data
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/WG 3	Trustworthiness
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/WG 4	Use cases and applications
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/WG 5	Computational approaches and computational characteristics of AI systems

g.iii Standards:

7 published ISO standards
<https://www.iso.org/committee/654019/x/catalogue/p/1/u/0/w/0/d/0>, but we consider relevant for GLOMICAVE the following:

- ISO/IEC 20546:2019 Information technology — Big data — Overview and vocabulary
 Scope:
 This document provides a set of terms and definitions needed to promote improved communication and understanding of big data and provides a terminological foundation for big data-related standards.
 This document provides a conceptual overview of the field of big data, its relationship to other technical areas and standards, and the concepts ascribed to big data that are not new to big data.
- ISO/IEC TR 20547-1:2020 Information technology — Big data reference architecture — Part 1: Framework and application process
 Scope:
 This document describes the framework of the big data reference architecture and the process for how a user of the architecture can apply it to their particular problem domain.
- ISO/IEC TR 20547-2:2018 Information technology — Big data reference architecture — Part 2: Use cases and derived requirements
 Scope:
 This document provides examples of big data use cases with application domains and technical considerations derived from contributed use cases.
- ISO/IEC TR 20547-3:2020 Information technology — Big data reference architecture — Part 3: Reference architecture
 Scope:
 This document specifies the big data reference architecture (BDRA). The reference architecture includes concepts and architectural views.
 The reference architecture specified in this document defines two architectural viewpoints:
 - a user view defining roles/sub-roles, their relationships, and types of activities within a big data ecosystem;
 - a functional view defining the architectural layers and the classes of functional components within those layers that implement the activities of the roles/sub-roles within the user view.
 The BDRA is intended to:
 - provide a common language for the various stakeholders;
 - encourage adherence to common standards, specifications, and patterns;
 - provide consistency of implementation of technology to solve similar problem sets;
 - facilitate the understanding of the operational intricacies in big data;
 - illustrate and understand the various big data components, processes, and systems, in the context of an overall big data conceptual model;
 - provide a technical reference for government departments, agencies and other consumers to understand, discuss, categorize and compare big data solutions; and
 - facilitate the analysis of candidate standards for interoperability, portability, reusability, and extensibility.
- ISO/IEC TR 20547-4:2020 Information technology — Big data reference architecture — Part 4: Security and privacy
 Scope:
 This document specifies the security and privacy aspects applicable to the big data reference architecture (BDRA) including data roles, activities and functional components and also provides guidance on security and privacy operations for big data.
- ISO/IEC TR 20547-5:2018 Information technology — Big data reference architecture — Part 5: Standards roadmap
 Scope:
 This document describes big data relevant standards, both in existence and under development, along with priorities for future standards development based on gap analysis.
- ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020 Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of trustworthiness in artificial intelligence

Scope:

This document surveys topics related to trustworthiness in AI systems, including the following:

- approaches to establish trust in AI systems through transparency, explainability, controllability, etc.;
- engineering pitfalls and typical associated threats and risks to AI systems, along with possible mitigation techniques and methods; and
- approaches to assess and achieve availability, resiliency, reliability, accuracy, safety, security and privacy of AI systems.

The specification of levels of trustworthiness for AI systems is out of the scope of this document.

g.iv Project of standards:

- ISO/IEC AWI 24029-2 Artificial intelligence (AI) — Assessment of the robustness of neural networks — Part 2: Methodology for the use of formal methods
- ISO/IEC WD TS 4213 Information technology — Artificial Intelligence — Assessment of machine learning classification performance
- ISO/IEC WD 5259-1 Data quality for analytics and ML — Part 1: Overview, terminology, and examples
- ISO/IEC AWI 5259-2 Data quality for analytics and ML — Part 2: Part 2: Data quality measures
- ISO/IEC WD 5259-3 Data quality for analytics and ML — Part 3: Data quality management requirements and guidelines
- ISO/IEC WD 5259-4 Data quality for analytics and ML — Part 4: Data quality process framework
- ISO/IEC WD 5338 Information technology — Artificial intelligence — AI system life cycle processes
- ISO/IEC WD 5339 Information Technology — Artificial Intelligence — Guidelines for AI applications
- ISO/IEC WD 5392 Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Reference architecture of knowledge engineering
- ISO/IEC AWI TS 6254 Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Objectives and methods for explainability of ML models and AI systems
- ISO/IEC AWI TR 24368 Information technology — Artificial intelligence — **Overview of ethical and societal concerns**
- ISO/IEC AWI 25059 Software engineering — Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) — Quality model for AI-based systems
- ISO/IEC AWI 42001 Information Technology — Artificial intelligence — Management system
- ISO/IEC DTR 24372 Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) — Overview of computational approaches for AI systems
- ISO/IEC CD 22989.2 **Artificial intelligence — Concepts and terminology**
- ISO/IEC CD 23053.2 **Framework for Artificial Intelligence (AI) Systems Using Machine Learning (ML)**
- ISO/IEC CD 23894 Information Technology — Artificial Intelligence — Risk Management
- ISO/IEC DTR 24027 Information technology — Artificial Intelligence (AI) — Bias in AI systems and AI aided decision making
- ISO/IEC CD 24668 Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Process management framework for Big data analytics
- ISO/IEC DIS 38507 Information technology — Governance of IT — Governance implications of the use of artificial intelligence by organizations
- ISO/IEC PRF TR 24030 Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) — Use cases

3.3 Environmental management

Technical Committee: **ISO/TC 207 Environmental management**

i. Scope:

Standardization in the field of environmental management to address environmental and climate impacts, including related social and economic aspects, in support of sustainable development.

Excluded:

- test methods of pollutants, setting limit values and levels of environmental performance, and standardization of products.

Note 1: TC 207 is focused on environmental management systems, auditing, verification/validation and related investigations, environmental labelling, environmental performance evaluation, life cycle assessment, climate change and its mitigation and adaptation, ecodesign, material efficiency, environmental economics and environmental and climate finance.

Note 2: Where appropriate, the ISO/TC 207 works in cooperation with existing committees on subjects that may support environmental management.

ii. Structure:

ISO/TC 207/SC 1	Environmental management systems
ISO/TC 207/SC 2	Environmental auditing and related environmental investigations
ISO/TC 207/SC 3	Environmental labelling
ISO/TC 207/SC 4	Environmental performance evaluation
ISO/TC 207/SC 5	Life cycle assessment
ISO/TC 207/SC 7	Greenhouse gas management and related activities
ISO/TC 207/DCCG	Developing Countries Coordination Group
ISO/TC 207/SLG	Strategic Leadership Group
ISO/TC 207/STTF	Spanish translation task force
ISO/TC 207/TCG	Terminology Coordination Group
ISO/TC 207/TG 1	Sustainable Finance Coordination
ISO/TC 207/TG 2	Circular economy coordination

iii. Standards:

51 published ISO standards
<https://www.iso.org/committee/54808/x/catalogue/p/1/u/0/w/0/d/0>, but we consider relevant for GLOMICAVE the following:

- ISO 14016:2020 Environmental management – Guidelines on the assurance of environmental information

Scope:

This document gives principles and guidelines for assuring the environmental information an organization includes in its environmental reports.

This document is applicable to assuring other types of reports in principle provided that special consideration is paid to identifying the competence needed by the assurance provider.

- ISO 14033:2019 Environmental management – Quantitative environmental information – Guidelines and examples

Scope:

This document gives guidelines for the systematic and methodical acquisition and review of quantitative environmental information and data about systems. It supports the application of standards and reports on environmental management.

This document gives guidelines for organizations on the general principles, policies, strategies and activities necessary to obtain quantitative environmental information for internal and/or external purposes. Such purposes can be, for example, to establish inventory routines and support decision making related to environmental policies and strategies, aimed in particular at comparing quantitative environmental information. The information is related to organizations, activities, facilities, technologies and products.

This document addresses issues related to defining, collecting, processing, interpreting and presenting quantitative environmental information. It provides guidelines on how to establish accuracy, verifiability and reliability for the intended use. It uses proven and well-established approaches for the preparation of information adapted to the specific needs of environmental management.

This document is applicable to all organizations, regardless of their size, type, location, structure, activities, products, level of development and whether or not they have an environmental management system in place.

NOTE 1 Quantitative information specifically addresses quantification of environmental performance in the form of environmental performance indicators in accordance with ISO 14031.

NOTE 2 Quantitative information also addresses quantification of risk for risk management purposes.

This document supplements the contents of other International Standards on environmental management.

NOTE 3 Annexes A and B provide illustrative and general examples of how to apply the guidelines and the framework. Annexes C and D provide sector-specific case studies on the application of the framework and case studies on selected documents from the ISO 14000 family, respectively. Annex E provides explanatory information to prevent misinterpretation of the guidance of this document.

- ISO 14040:2006 Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Principles and framework

Scope:

This International Standard describes the principles and framework for life cycle assessment (LCA) including

- a) the goal and scope definition of the LCA,
- b) the life cycle inventory analysis (LCI) phase,
- c) the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) phase,
- d) the life cycle interpretation phase,
- e) reporting and critical review of the LCA,
- f) limitations of the LCA,
- g) relationship between the LCA phases, and
- h) conditions for use of value choices and optional elements.

This International Standard covers life cycle assessment (LCA) studies and life cycle inventory (LCI) studies. It does not describe the LCA technique in detail, nor does it specify methodologies for the individual phases of the LCA.

The intended application of LCA or LCI results is considered during the goal and scope definition, but the application itself is outside the scope of this International Standard.

This International Standard is not intended for contractual or regulatory purposes or registration and certification.

- ISO 14044:2006 Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Requirements and guidelines

Scope:

This International Standard specifies requirements and provides guidelines for life cycle assessment (LCA) including

- a) the goal and scope definition of the LCA,
- b) the life cycle inventory analysis (LCI) phase,
- c) the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) phase,
- d) the life cycle interpretation phase,
- e) reporting and critical review of the LCA,
- f) limitations of the LCA,
- g) relationship between the LCA phases, and
- h) conditions for use of value choices and optional elements.

This International Standard covers life cycle assessment (LCA) studies and life cycle inventory (LCI) studies.

The intended application of LCA or LCI results is considered during the goal and scope definition, but the application itself is outside the scope of this International Standard.

This International Standard is not intended for contractual or regulatory purposes or registration and certification.

iv. Project of standards:

- ISO/WD 14002-2 Environmental management systems – Guidelines for using ISO 14001 to address environmental aspects and conditions within an environmental topic area – Part 2: Water
- ISO/AWI 14015 Environmental management – Environmental Due Diligence Assessment (revision of ISO 14015:2001)
- ISO/CD 14017 Environmental management – Requirements with guidance for verification and validation of water statements
- ISO/CD 14020 Environmental labels and declarations — General principles
- ISO 14021:2016/FDAmD 1 Environmental labels and declarations — Self-declared environmental claims (Type II environmental labelling) — Amendment 1: Carbon footprint, carbon neutral
- ISO/WD TS 14029 Mutual recognition agreements between Type III Environmental Declaration (EPD) Programme Operators — Principles and procedures
- ISO/DIS 14030-1 Environmental performance evaluation — Green debt instruments — Part 1: Process for green bonds
- ISO/DIS 14030-2 Environmental performance evaluation — Green debt instruments — Part 2: Process for green loans
- ISO/DIS 14030-3 Environmental performance evaluation — Green debt instruments — Part 3: Taxonomy
- ISO/DIS 14030-4 Environmental performance evaluation — Green debt instruments — Part 4: Verification
- ISO 14031 Environmental management — Environmental performance evaluation — Guidelines
- ISO/CD TR 14035 Environmental technology verification — ETV - Guidance to implement ISO 14034
- ISO/CD 14100 Green Finance: Assessment of Green Financial Projects
- ISO/WD TR 14055-2 Environmental management — Guidelines for establishing good practices for combatting land degradation and desertification — Part 2: Regional case studies
- ISO/WD TS 14074 Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles, requirements and guidelines for normalization, weighting and interpretation
- ISO/AWI 59014 Secondary materials — Principles, sustainability and traceability requirements
- ISO/WD 14068 Greenhouse gas management and related activities — Carbon neutrality
- ISO/CD TR 14069 Greenhouse gases — Quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions for organizations — Guidance for the application of ISO 14064-1
- ISO/AWI TR 14082 Radiative Forcing Management— Guidance for the quantification and reporting of radiative forcing-based climate footprints and mitigation efforts
- ISO/AWI 14083 Greenhouse gases — Quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions arising from operations of transport chains
- ISO/AWI 14093 Mechanism for financing local adaptation to climate change: Performance-based climate resilience grants
- ISO/FDIS 14097 Greenhouse gas management and related activities — Framework including principles and requirements for assessing and reporting investments and financing activities related to climate change
- ISO/FDIS 19694-1 Stationary source emissions — Determination of greenhouse gas emissions in energy-intensive industries — Part 1: General aspects

3.4 Food products

Technical Committee: **ISO/TC 34 Food products**

i. Scope:

Standardization in the field of human and animal foodstuffs, covering the food chain from primary production to consumption, as well as animal and vegetable propagation materials, in particular, but not limited to, terminology, sampling, methods of test and analysis, product specifications, food and feed safety and quality management and requirements for packaging, storage and transportation

Excluded:

- products covered by ISO/TC 54 *Essential oils* and ISO/TC 93 *Starch (including derivatives and by-products)*.

ii. Structure:

ISO/TC 34/SC 2	Oleaginous seeds and fruits and oilseed meals
ISO/TC 34/SC 3	Fruits and vegetables and their derived products
ISO/TC 34/SC 4	Cereals and pulses
ISO/TC 34/SC 5	Milk and milk products
ISO/TC 34/SC 6	Meat, poultry, fish, eggs and their products
ISO/TC 34/SC 7	Spices, culinary herbs and condiments
ISO/TC 34/SC 8	Tea
ISO/TC 34/SC 9	Microbiology
ISO/TC 34/SC 10	Animal feeding stuffs
ISO/TC 34/SC 11	Animal and vegetable fats and oils
ISO/TC 34/SC 12	Sensory analysis
ISO/TC 34/SC 15	Coffee
ISO/TC 34/SC 16	Horizontal methods for molecular biomarker analysis
ISO/TC 34/SC 17	Management systems for food safety
ISO/TC 34/SC 18	Cocoa
ISO/TC 34/SC 19	Bee products
ISO/TC 34/CAG	Chairmen Advisory group
ISO/TC 34/WG 14	Vitamins, carotenoids and other nutrients
ISO/TC 34/WG 16	Animal welfare
ISO/TC 34/WG 20	Aflatoxins
ISO/TC 34/WG 21	Social responsibility/sustainability
ISO/TC 34/WG 22	Natural antimicrobial
ISO/TC 34/WG 23	Food suitable for vegetarians/vegans
ISO/TC 34/WG 24	qNMR (Quantitative nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy)
ISO/TC 34/WG 25	Food security in emergency or crisis situation

iii. Standards:

899 published ISO standards
<https://www.iso.org/committee/47858/x/catalogue/p/1/u/0/w/0/d/0>, but we consider relevant for GLOMICAVE the following:

- ISO 22000:2018 Food safety management systems – Requirements for any organization in the food chain

Scope:

This document specifies requirements for a food safety management system (FSMS) to enable an organization that is directly or indirectly involved in the food chain:

- a) to plan, implement, operate, maintain and update a FSMS providing products and services that are safe, in accordance with their intended use;
- b) to demonstrate compliance with applicable statutory and regulatory food safety requirements;
- c) to evaluate and assess mutually agreed customer food safety requirements and to demonstrate conformity with them;
- d) to effectively communicate food safety issues to interested parties within the food chain;
- e) to ensure that the organization conforms to its stated food safety policy;
- f) to demonstrate conformity to relevant interested parties;
- g) to seek certification or registration of its FSMS by an external organization, or make a self-assessment or self-declaration of conformity to this document.

All requirements of this document are generic and are intended to be applicable to all organizations in the food chain, regardless of size and complexity. Organizations that are directly or indirectly involved include, but are not limited to, feed producers, animal food producers, harvesters of wild plants and animals, farmers, producers of ingredients, food manufacturers, retailers, and organizations providing food services, catering services, cleaning and sanitation services, transportation, storage and distribution services, suppliers of equipment, cleaning and disinfectants, packaging materials and other food contact materials.

This document allows any organization, including small and/or less developed organizations (e.g. a small farm, a small packer-distributor, a small retail or food service outlet) to implement externally- developed elements in their FSMS.

Internal and/or external resources can be used to meet the requirements of this document.

- ISO/TS 22002-5:2019 Prerequisite programmes on food safety – Part 5 – Transport and storage

Scope:

This document specifies requirements for establishing, implementing and maintaining prerequisite programmes (PRPs) for transport and storage in the food chain to assist in controlling food safety hazards.

This document is applicable to all organizations, regardless of size or complexity, that are involved in transport and storage activities across the food supply chain and that wish to implement PRPs in such a way as to address the requirements specified in [ISO 22000](#).

This document is neither designed nor intended for use in other parts of the food supply chain or in isolation.

In this document, transport and storage is aligned with [ISO/TS 22003:2013, Annex A, Category G](#). This document includes all food and feed products and food packaging and packaging materials.

Live animals are excluded from the scope of this document except when intended for direct consumption, e.g. molluscs, crustaceans and live fish.

- ISO/TS 22002-6:2016 Prerequisite programmes on food safety – Part 6 – Feed and animal food production

Scope:

This Technical Specification specifies requirements for establishing, implementing and maintaining prerequisite programmes (PRPs) to assist in controlling feed safety hazards in feed and animal food and in materials intended for use in the production of feed and animal food. Feed safety hazards in this context relate to attributes that have a potential to affect adversely animal and/or human health.

Prerequisite programmes are intended to ensure feed safety and to prevent, control and detect potential contamination including cross-contamination that could occur under the responsibility of the organization.

This Technical Specification is applicable to all organizations regardless of size, location or complexity that are involved in the manufacturing and/or supply of feed and animal food and wish to implement a PRP. Feed and animal food operations are diverse in nature and not all of the requirements specified in this Technical Specification necessarily apply to an individual organization or process. Where exclusions are made or alternative measures are implemented, these need to be justified by a hazard assessment and verified to be effective. Any exclusions or alternative measures adopted should not affect the ability of an organization to comply with other requirements contained in this Technical Specification.

- ISO 22005:2007 Traceability in the feed and food chain – General principles and basic requirements for system design and implementation

Scope:

This International Standard gives the principles and specifies basic requirements for the design and implementation of a feed and food traceability system. It can be applied by an organization operating at any step in the feed and food chain.

It is intended to be flexible enough to allow feed organizations and food organizations to achieve identified objectives.

The traceability system is a technical tool to assist an organization to conform with its defined objectives and is applicable when necessary to determine the history, or location of a product or its relevant components.

iv. Project of standards:

97 project of standards under development <https://www.iso.org/committee/47858/x/catalogue/p/0/u/1/w/0/d/0>, but we consider relevant for GLOMICAVE the following:

- ISO/DIS 22753 Molecular biomarker analysis – Method for the statistical evaluation of analytical results obtained in testing sub-sampled groups of genetically modified seeds and grains – General requirements and definitions
- ISO/DIS 23418 Microbiology of the food chain – Whole genome sequencing for typing and genomic characterization of foodborne bacteria – General requirements and guidance

3.5 Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment and disposal

Technical Committee:

1. ISO/TC 275 Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment and disposal

i. Scope:

Standardization of the methods for characterizing, categorizing, preparing, treating, recycling and managing sludge and products from urban wastewater collection systems, night soil, storm water handling, water supply treatment plants, wastewater treatment plants for urban and similar industrial waters. It includes all sludge that may have similar environmental and/or health impacts.

Standardization of measurement methods for characterizing and categorizing encompasses: sampling methods, physical, chemical and microbiological parameters analysis, preparation of sludge, physical behaviour of sludge, all required for the characterization of sludge with a view to facilitate decisions on the choice of the treatment procedures and of the use and disposal of sludge.

Excluded:

hazardous sludge from industry and dredged sludge already covered by ISO/TC 190 "Soil Quality"

ii. Structure:

ISO/TC 275/WG 1	Terminology
ISO/TC 275/WG 2	Characterization methods
ISO/TC 275/WG 3	Anaerobic digestion
ISO/TC 275/WG 4	Land application
ISO/TC 275/WG 5	Thermal processes
ISO/TC 275/WG 6	Thickening and dewatering
ISO/TC 275/WG 7	Inorganics and nutrients recovery
ISO/TC 275/WG 8	Communication and Management of Public Perception

iii. Standards:

1 published ISO standards <https://www.iso.org/committee/4493530/x/catalogue/p/1/u/0/w/0/d/0>

- ISO 19698:2020 Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment and disposal — Beneficial use of biosolids — Land application

Scope:

This document provides guidance on the conditions of beneficial use of biosolids produced from industrial and municipal sludge and municipal biosolids derived products (e.g. composts, growing media) in the production of food and feed crops, energy crops, forestry crops and for the remediation of disturbed sites.

This document applies to biosolids for land application and includes biosolids from wastewater treatment (municipal, industrial and private onsite systems).

This document does not apply to hazardous sludge that originates from wastewater which, due to its nature, physical, chemical or infectious properties, is potentially hazardous to human health and/or the environment during use, handling, storage or transportation and which requires special disposal techniques to eliminate or reduce the hazard.

This document includes:

- general guidelines for the land application of biosolids and biosolids derived products;
- specific guidelines for the land application of biosolids and biosolids derived products for food and feed crop production and for non-food and non-feed crop production (e.g. horticulture, fibre for bio-mass, silviculture, etc.); and
- specific guidelines for the land application of biosolids and biosolids derived products for other beneficial uses (e.g. land reclamation or rehabilitation).

iv. Project of standards:

8 projects of ISO standards under development <https://www.iso.org/committee/4493530/x/catalogue/p/0/u/1/w/0/d/0>, but we consider relevant for GLOMICAVE the following:

- ISO/CD 19388 Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment and disposal — Guidelines for the operation of anaerobic digestion facilities

4. CONCLUSIONS

As a result of the review of the standardization landscape through the methodology explained above, the following conclusion may be drawn:

There is a large number of mainly International technical committees, as well as of standards and project standards related to GLOMICAVE project that may be useful for its development and also for its future dissemination. Despite there are not a specific standardization technical committee which activity impacts directly in the GLOMICAVE project, specific tasks to be addressed in the project are related with standardization works. Depending on the assessment by GLOMICAVE partners of the impact of the identified standardization committees on their tasks and the level of contribution that their results can represent for these committees and for the development of Deliverable D7.4 (Report on the contribution to standardization), several actions can be performed, for example:

- the follow up of the standardization activity through updates reported by UNE;
- the follow up through the joining of one or more GLOMICAVE representatives to the above standardization committees. Standardization is an open activity, and all interested parties may participate in a CEN/CENELEC/ISO/IEC technical committee through its National Mirror Committee and its National Standardization Body;
- the dissemination of the GLOMICAVE project progress by delivering reports to the relevant TCs Secretaries or by attending relevant technical committees' meetings.

With respect the dissemination activities, the most relevant committees are summarized in the following table:

Table 3 –Main technical committees for dissemination activities.

Subject	Technical committee
Biogas	- ISO/TC 255 Biogas
Information technology	- ISO/IEC JTC1 Information technology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o ISO/IEC JTC1/SC23 Digitally recorded media for information interchange and storage o ISO/IEC JTC1/ SC25 Interconnection of information technology equipment o ISO/IEC JTC1/SC27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection o ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29 Coding of audio, picture, multimedia and hypermedia information o ISO/IEC JTC1/SC32 Data management and interchange o ISO/IEC JTC1/SC38 Cloud computing and distributed platforms o ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 Artificial intelligence
Environmental management	- ISO/TC 207 Environmental management
Food products	- ISO/TC 34 Food products
Sludge recovery, recycling treatment and disposal	- ISO/TC 275 Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment and disposal

To achieve these objectives, further assessments will be performed by the partners to determine the type of interaction to be established with the identified standardization technical committees. The ways of interaction of the project with the standardization committees could include:

- The participation of one or more GLOMICAVE partners in the standardization technical committees. Standardization is an open activity, and all interested parties may participate in a CEN/CENELEC, ISO/IEC technical committee through the designation of National Standardization Bodies/National Mirror Committee;
- The participation through the formal liaison of the GLOMICAVE project with International standardization committees to participate directly as liaison organization which intends to make technical contributions to their works. This option would be further analysed since there is not a formal standardization activity at European level;
- The dissemination of the GLOMICAVE project progress by delivering reports to the relevant standardization technical committees or by participation of GLOMICAVE partners in the relevant technical committees meetings;
- Feeding the standardization committees with standardization proposals coming from identified gaps and needs.

Additionally, the activity of the standardization committees required will be periodically reported by UNE.

Following the present deliverable, above options will be analysed with the partners to determine the most suitable way to contribute to future standards with the results and approach of the project. In addition, it will be decided which standardization committees will be addressed and how for disseminating the results. These will be the first steps towards D7.4 “Report on the contribution to standardization” to be delivered in M42 which will contain the steps and progress of the interaction with the standardization system.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] CENELEC Website (www.cenelec.eu)
- [2] CEN/CENELEC Projex Online database (projex.cen.eu) (restricted to authorized users)
- [3] ISO Website (www.iso.org)
- [4] ISO Project Portal (isotc.iso.org) (restricted to authorized users)
- [5] IEC Website (www.iec.ch)
- [6] Online Browsing Platform (OBP, <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/>)